

BILINGUALISM. BILINGUAL EDUCATION IN SCHOOL

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Annotation

This article provides information on the structure of the Bilingual education system, its achievements, as well as the specific features of Bilingual education

Keywords: Bilingualism, bilingual education, multilingual, educational system, practical part.

Аннотация

В данной статье представлена информация о структуре системы билингвального образования, ее достижениях, а также особенностях билингвального образования

Ключевые слова: Билингвизм, двуязычное образование, полиязычие, начальная школа, практическая часть.

Bilingualism refers to the ability to use two languages in everyday life. Bilingualism is common and is on the rise in many parts of the world, with perhaps one in three people being bilingual or multilingual.

Defining bilingualism in just a few words is not easy, as each individual has different bilingual characteristics. There may be distinctions between ability and use of a language, or differences in proficiency between the two languages.

Bilingual education in primary school. Results. Achievements.

In primary school, the curriculum is bilingual for all students, while in secondary school we continue the bilingual programme, but there is also a possibility of a full programme in English. This enables the students to acquire a variety of language skills and to become aware of the world around them. Mastering two languages enhances thinking skills, facilitates the integration of complex concepts, and makes it easier to understand different cultures and ways of thinking. Numerous studies show that bilingual learners have a better memory capacity and greater mental flexibility. They perform better at school than monolinguals. I made a some experience between ordinary pupils and bilingual pupils. English was the subject of the 45-minute lesson. There were 25 students in the Year 4 class, roughly 15 of them spoke Uzbek as their mother tongue, while the remaining students were (or appeared to be) monolingual. The lesson's material was drawn from the theme "knowledge and understanding of places, patterns, and processes" and was intended to fulfill the requirement for studying two localities: Uzbek and Tajik. These languages are easily accessible for such lessons, and

a well-liked set for schools with a sizable population of students with Tajik heritage backgrounds covers the in Tajikistan and includes a well-made video. This cultural and social understanding informed me. The purpose of my topic was to increase the kids' awareness of the disparities and parallels between the community they lived in in West Yorkshire and what they saw in the film. The majority of the lesson time was spent with the class watching portions of the film together, interspersed with questions and discussion. At least seven times during the course of the session, there were extensive discussions between Uzbek and Tajik, as well as shorter ones. Overall, I had the impression that the session was well-organized and conducted, with lengthy discussions designed to involve all of the students present. Despite English being the language of choice, Tajik had its place. The children who were 'monolingual' sat quietly and appeared to be paying attention, while the other children who spoke Tajiki appeared to be listening closely to what was going on. Overall, I had the impression that the session was well-organized and conducted, with lengthy discussions designed to involve all of the students present. Despite English being the language of choice, Tajik had its place. I wrote down the instruction.

In conclusion, there is no doubt that bilingual educators could make a significant contribution to the transformative teaching and learning that if their system recognizes the potential of their bilingualism and supports the growth of it as a component of their professional expertise. First declaration that such pedagogies can be used by all educators, not simply those who share the language and cultural backgrounds of their students, despite the fact that this chapter has mostly focused on bilingual teachers. It should be said that the research and general results show the positive side of bilingualism. The main role of this is that students with dual languages in reading have stronger intellectual capacity and different results than normal students.

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